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Residential energy demand, emissions, and expenditures at regional and income-decile level for alternative futures

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Summary

Income and its distribution profile are important determinants of residential energy demand and carry direct implications for human well-being and climate. We explore the sensitivity of residential energy systems to income growth and distribution across SSP-RCP scenarios using a global, integrated, multisector dynamics model, GCAM, which tracks national/regional household energy services and fuel choice by income decile. Nation/region energy use patterns across deciles tend to converge over time with aggregate income growth, as higher-income consumers approach satiation levels in floorspace and energy services. However, in some regions, existing within-region inequalities in energy consumption persist over time due to slow income growth in lower income groups. Due to continued differences in fuel types, lower income groups will have higher exposure to household air pollution, despite lower contributions to greenhouse gas emissions. We also find that the share of income dedicated to energy is higher for lower deciles, with strong regional differences.

Keywords: Energy demand; Socioeconomic pathways; Household energy access; Emissions; Energy expenditures.

Introduction

Building energy represents around 33% of total final energy demand at a global level, with 23% associated with the residential sector, and 10% with the commercial sector¹. Global residential energy access has significantly increased in the last 40 years, with a subsequent increase in household energy consumption². However, the progress has been slowed down in the last decade, with around 31% of the world's population still lacking access to clean residential energy in 2020³, and, therefore, residential energy consumption in the last decade has increased at significantly lower rates². Increasing household energy access and consumption further in the coming decades will become essential for improving the living standards and boost human development, particularly in the Global South⁴⁻⁹. Nevertheless, the direct fuel use and electricity consumption in the residential sector account for 17% of global energy-related carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions¹⁰. Likewise, the building sector is a major source of non-CO₂ greenhouse gases (GHG) and air pollutants^{11,12}, with direct impact for the global climate system¹³. The building sector directly interacts with other sectors of the economy. Therefore, the evolution of the residential energy demand and the composition of the household energy mix will have socioeconomic and planetary implications for the agriculture, forest, and land-use (AFOLU), water, or climate systems^{14,15} across multiple scales, which need to be addressed from a holistic perspective.

The evolution of future energy demand will be driven by uncertain socioeconomic conditions and/or low-carbon transition goals, which makes it necessary to develop a range of narratives that represent alternative futures^{16,17}. Some of the most extensively-used scenarios to address these uncertainties and represent alternative and homogenized narratives for the forward-looking analysis of the climate-energy-land-water (CLEW) systems are the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs)¹⁸. These scenarios provide different and plausible trends for the quantification of demographic, socioeconomic, and technological factors that can be fed into integrated assessment models to explore alternative futures^{19,20}. Indeed, the SSP scenarios have been applied in more than 700 scientific studies¹⁶ since their release, and they have become a central element for the global scenario and regional analysis, including the latest assessment reports by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). Focusing on the building sector, several studies have estimated future residential and/or commercial energy demand and the subsequent emission impacts for alternative futures which include different SSP narratives and/or the potential transition to a low-carbon economy²¹⁻²⁶. These studies show how building energy demand will vary as a response to changes in future demographics, income growth, climate, building shell conductivity, technology efficiency, or lifestyle changes. Nevertheless, most of these studies project future energy demand at a national or supra-national level, and do not explore the distributional implications for different socioeconomic groups within each region.

The use of a single representative consumer, modeled using average GDP/cap, to drive demand within a region has been the standard approach in the integrated assessment of global scenarios (including SSPs), while the literature has extensively discussed the importance of moving from aggregate projections to more disaggregated scales²⁷⁻³¹. Considering the relation between residential energy and human development, the consumer-level perspective becomes even more important for the forward-looking analysis of the household energy demand. In a previous study, we demonstrated the importance of considering within-region population heterogeneity by showing that if U.S. states transition to either a more or less equal income distribution, it will have a direct impact on the level of aggregate future energy demand³². While the study had a single-region perspective and the scenarios were purely illustrative, it demonstrated how considering within-region population heterogeneity affects our understanding of future residential energy demand. Other studies have explored future residential energy demand for different socioeconomic groups, showing how the existing differences across these groups will project into the future under alternative scenarios³³⁻³⁶. However, these studies are limited either geographically or temporally, or focus only on

energy demand, without exploring additional multisectoral interactions. To our knowledge, this is the first study that explores the evolution of global residential energy and service demands at regional and income-decile level for alternative SSP-RCP (Representative Concentration Pathways^{37,38}) narratives (see Table S1) and income distribution pathways, incorporating income-group-specific demand responses based on a functional form generated from empirical data. In addition, the fully-coupled model used in this study allows the capture of additional direct and indirect multisector implications in terms of greenhouse gas (GHG) and air pollutant emissions and energy expenditures.

Methodology

The analysis has been developed using the Global Change Analysis Model (GCAM), which is designed to analyze human and physical Earth-system dynamics, by exploring the behavior and interdependencies between the economy, energy, water, climate, and agriculture, forestry, and land use (AFOLU) systems^{39–41}. GCAM allows quantification and exploration of the implications of alternative uncertain futures within a single, unified computational platform. The model represents the entire world with different scales for different systems: the energy-economy system operates at 32 geopolitical supra-regions; land system is divided 384 land subregions, which combine geopolitical regions with 233 water basins; the Earth-system module operates at a global scale.

In this study, we have developed an enhanced version of GCAM-v6.0, which includes: 1) a series of modifications to better capture the dynamics of the building sector; 2) consumer heterogeneity in the residential sector in the form of income deciles (instead of using an average representative consumer).

GCAM divides the buildings sector between commercial and residential buildings and estimates future floorspace and energy service demand based on alternative equations that have been calibrated analyzing cross-regional historical data. Per capita residential floorspace in period t , region r , and for decile i is estimated using a Gompertz-type function of income ($GDPpc$), population density (PD), a satiation level ($UnadjSat$), and different calibration parameters (a , b , c). Total floorspace is calculated as the product of per capita floorspace and population.

$$F_{t,r,i} = (UnadjSat_r - a * \ln(PD_{t,r})) * \exp(-b * \exp(-c * \ln(GDPpc_{t,r,i}))) + k_r \quad (1)$$

In this enhanced model version, demand for residential energy is divided between modern and traditional energy services, which are disaggregated in three end-use demand sectors – heating (h), cooling (c), and non-thermal/others (o). Modern fuels include electricity, natural gas, refined liquids, commercial biomass, hydrogen, and district heat, while traditional fuels are traditional biomass and coal. Demand for (modern) heating (Eq 2), cooling (Eq 3), and non-thermal (Eq 4) services are summarized in the following equations:

$$h_{t,r,i} = k_{h,r} * (HDD_{t,r} * \eta_{r,t,i} * R_r + \lambda_{h,r} * IG_{t,r,i}) * \left[1 - \exp\left(-\frac{\ln(2)}{\mu_{h,r}} * \frac{GDPpc_{t,r,i}}{Ph_{t,r}}\right) \right] + a_{h,r} \quad (2)$$

$$c_{t,r,i} = k_{c,r} * (CDD_{t,r} * \eta_{r,t,i} * R_r + \lambda_{c,r} * IG_{t,r,i}) * \left[1 - \exp\left(-\frac{\ln(2)}{\mu_{c,r}} * \frac{GDPpc_{t,r,i}}{Pc_{t,r}}\right) \right] + a_{c,r} \quad (3)$$

$$o_{t,r,i} = k_{o,r} * \left[1 - \exp \left(- \frac{\ln(2)}{\mu_{o,r}} * \frac{GDPpc_{t,r,i}}{Po_{t,r}} \right) \right] + a_{o,r} \quad (4)$$

Equations 2-4 show that demand for modern services is driven by a satiation level (k), income ($GDPpc$), service prices (P), calibration parameters (μ , a), and a “thermal load” that consist of heating/cooling degree days (HDD/CDD), buildings shell conductivity (η), the floorspace-to-surface ratio (R), and the internal gains associated with the heat released by non-thermal energy services (escalated by region, λ).

Empirical evidence shows that demand for traditional services (coal and traditional biomass) rapidly decreases as income rises. Demand for traditional service s , from fuel f , region r , period t , and decile i is driven by income ($GDPpc$), service price (P) and calibration parameters (X , Y , a), as summarized in the following equation:

$$d_{t,r,i,f,s} = \frac{X_{f,s}}{\frac{GDPpc_{t,r,i}}{P_{t,r,f,s}} + Y_{f,s}} + a_{r,f,s} \quad (5)$$

GCAM includes alternative energy sources for producing each residential energy service. Note that not all energy sources can be used for producing all services (e.g., there is no cooling with refined liquids). The energy competition between fuels in GCAM follows a modified logit choice model⁴², which prevents a winner-take-all response. The use of a logit model allows to capture some regionally specific preferences for particular choice alternatives (e.g., societal preferences), and allows new technologies to be phased in gradually, which will have direct impact in the future residential energy mix. This logit model is detailed in online documentation (<https://github.com/JGCRI/gcam-doc/blob/gh-pages/choice.md>), and in the Supplementary Information (SI).

For the implementation of the SSP scenarios in GCAM, we apply SSP-specific population and average GDP growth rates from existing literature^{43,44}. Income distribution pathways are taken from Narayan et al, (2023)⁴⁵, that uses a non-parametric approach (i.e., principal component analysis) to project net-income-deciles for all countries by the end of the century. We also implement SSP-specific parameters for the energy system (fossil fuel extraction and costs, electricity and energy production costs, or fuel-technology preferences), the AFOLU system (yield productivity changes, food and/or meat demand, or trade preferences), and air pollutant emission factors. More details on the SSP implementation in GCAM can be found in the SI, online model documentation (<https://github.com/JGCRI/gcam-doc/blob/gh-pages/ssp.md>), and in Calvin et al, (2017)⁴⁶. The RCP scenarios are based on a long-term system-wide transformation in the methods of production and consumption, with a rapid transition towards non-emitting energy sources. For the implementation, we exogenously implement a long-term objective on radiative forcing and the model internally calculates a shadow carbon price that achieves that objective. More details can be found in the SI (section “*Scenario Description*”).

In this version, demand for residential energy is projected by income deciles, which have been generated based on different historical data on income distributions. Given that there is no global data on residential floorspace and energy service demand at income decile level, the allocation of regional data across different deciles has been carried out making use of the calibrated floorspace and energy service demand functions. The details on these calibration procedures can be found in the SI. Once the income deciles are calibrated, the model projects future floorspace, residential service and energy demands, and direct greenhouse gas (GHG) and air pollutant emissions at decile level. The SI includes additional information on the functional forms, model calibration, implementation of the multiple consumers (i.e., deciles), the subsector/fuel competition, or the estimation of the emissions associated with the residential sector (see SI, “*Global*”).

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3 *Change Analysis Model (GCAM)*). Moreover, the SI also includes a detailed description of the analyzed
4 scenarios, including the implementation details (see SI, “*Scenario description*”). We note that, in this study,
5 we show results for a representative subset of five regions in order to show the effects in regions with
6 largely different geographical and socioeconomic features. However, figures can be easily replicated for
7 any of the 32 geopolitical regions in the model, just by adding a new region name in the script provided to
8 replicate the results (see “*Data and code availability*”).
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10 Finally, to visualize changes in the within-region inequalities in energy access, we calculate energy-service-
11 specific Palma ratios⁴⁷ and Gini coefficients⁴⁸. In order to focus on the differences between top and bottom
12 income deciles, most results are focused on the Palma ratio, while the Gini coefficients are provided in the
13 SI. The Palma ratio represents the modern energy service demand of the top decile divided by the sum of
14 the demand of the bottom 40%.
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$$16 \quad \text{Palma ratio} = \frac{D_{10}}{\sum_{i=1}^4 D_i} \quad (6)$$

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22 **Results**

23 **Evolution of residential energy service demand**

24 Residential energy service demand depends on a range of different socioeconomic, technological, and
25 market factors, until a “satiation level” is achieved, which determines the “service comfort” above which
26 the marginal utility of an energy service becomes negative. Our results show that future energy service
27 demand increases over time in all the regions in the world (Figure 1), driven by growth of population (Figure
28 S5), per capita GDP (Figure S7), and floorspace, which is itself a function of GDP/cap and population
29 density (Figure S9). We find that, in high-income regions, consumers are closer to the satiation level and,
30 therefore, the rise in service demand is relatively lower than in low-income economies. This dynamic is
31 more pronounced for thermal (heating and cooling) than for non-thermal services. For example, heating
32 demand in the U.S. only increases around 22% from 2020 to 2050, as higher income deciles are already at
33 or near their satiation levels for heating demand and will not increase their room temperatures as their
34 income increases further. On the contrary, this increase is around 200% in Africa Eastern, Middle East, or
35 China, and more than 400% in India and South Asia, as their population begins further from the satiation
36 level and will rapidly increase their service demands as their incomes rise. The socioeconomic pathways
37 and additional economy-wide assumptions across SSP narratives have a direct impact on aggregated energy
38 service demand projections (Figure 1). In high-income economies such as EU-15 or the U.S., demand in
39 2050 will vary around -20% to +35%, compared to the central narrative (SSP2), depending on the service
40 and the SSP narrative. These uncertainty ranges in low-income economies are even larger and they can
41 represent up to -40% to +90% (compared to SSP2) in some regions and services (e.g., cooling in India).
42 The alternative RCP scenarios have also an effect on regional service demand due to price equilibrium
43 impacts, considering that the large changes in fuel prices associated with a low-carbon transition scenario
44 directly impact average service prices. However, the energy efficiency is exogenously parameterized in
45 GCAM (see SI), so there are no additional efficiency measures in the RCP scenarios. Therefore, the
46 reduction in total service demand in 2050 between the baseline and the RCP scenarios are relatively small,
47 accounting for less than 5%.
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Figure 1: Residential energy service demand per period, region, service, and scenario (EJ). The line represents the SSP2 narrative, while the shaded areas represent the uncertainty ranges associated with the alternative SSP narratives. The figure includes a subset of the GCAM regions that covers a range of income, population, and base year fuel mixes.

The composition of residential energy mix will also differ across SSP narratives and RCP scenarios (Figure 2). In the Baseline, in high-income economies, electricity dominates the cooling and the non-thermal sectors, while gas is the major source for heating, followed by other sources such as district heat, electricity, or refined liquids. In some low-income economies (e.g., Africa Eastern) traditional biomass is the major source for heating and non-thermal services in 2015, but it is gradually substituted by modern energy technologies (i.e., electricity) over time as per capita income increases. The different resource, fuel, and technology costs result in a residential energy mix that varies across SSP narratives, with the effects being particularly large for low-income economies. The transition to the low-carbon (RCP) scenarios directly reduces the consumption of the high-emitting fuel and technologies, such as refined liquids, district heat, or natural gas, due to the endogenous (shadow) price applied to these high-emitting technologies in order to achieve the RCP target (see SI). Electricity replaces these higher emitting fuels and becomes the largest energy source for all services, including heating. Focusing on the RCP2.6 scenario, residential electricity consumption, at a global level, increases from 23 EJ in 2015 to 73 (62 - 106) EJ in 2050, with the largest relative increase observed in low-income economies such as Africa Eastern, Africa Western, Africa Southern, or South Asia.

Figure 2: Composition of the residential energy mix per period, region, service, and scenario (EJ). The line represents the SSP2 narrative, while the shaded areas represent the uncertainty ranges associated with the alternative SSP narratives. The figure includes a subset of the GCAM regions that covers a range of income, population, and base year fuel mixes. The figure compares the Baseline with the most stringent RCP scenario (RCP2.6). Additional results for RCP4.5 and RCP6.0 can be found in the SI (Figure S10).

Focusing on within-region dynamics, our results indicate that, overall, demand for modern energy services increases over time in all regions and for all income deciles, driven by the growth of aggregate regional per capita GDP and floorspace demand, which are shown in the SI (Figure S4, Figure S8). However, the evolution of future residential energy services widely varies across regions and deciles. Lower-income deciles rapidly increase their floorspace demand as their income rises. In addition, they also increase their modern energy service demand (per unit of floorspace), substituting cleaner electricity and natural gas for

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3 traditional fuels. On the contrary, upper deciles, particularly in high-income regions, are closer to the
4 floorspace and energy service satiation levels, so their increase of residential energy service demand is
5 relatively lower. For example, in the U.S., the increase in total residential energy service demand from 2015
6 to 2050 accounts for 25% for the highest decile (D10), while it represents around a four-fold increase for
7 the lowest income group (D1), as D1 starts from a significantly lower value. This implies that, in general,
8 the differences in residential energy demand across deciles decreases over time. The implementation of
9 alternative SSP narratives and the transition to a low-carbon economy will have an impact on the demand
10 of both lower and upper deciles. Figure 3 shows the evolution of residential modern energy service demand
11 for the Baseline scenario, while the RCP scenarios are shown in the SI (Figure S11). Considering the effect
12 of the RCP scenarios in the composition of the residential energy mix, the SI includes additional information
13 on per capita service output for different scenarios, regions, services, deciles, and fuels (Figure S12 and
14 Figure S13).

17 **Figure 3: Evolution of residential modern energy service demand for the Baseline scenario per period, region, and service**
18 **(EJ)** The line represents the SSP2 narrative, while the shaded areas represent the uncertainty ranges associated with the alternative
19 SSP narratives. The figure includes a subset of the GCAM regions that covers a range of income, population, and base year fuel
20 mixes. Per capita results can be found in Figure S13 in the SI. The results for the RCP scenarios can be found in Figure S11 in the
21 SI.

48 As shown in Figure 4, there currently exist significant differences in modern energy access. Cooling is the
49 energy service with the highest level of observed inequality, particularly in low-income economies, where
50 the modern cooling demand of the top 10% is around ten times larger than the demand of the bottom 40%
51 in some regions like Africa Western (Palma ratio =14.1), Africa Southern (14), Central Asia (10.3), South
52 Africa (9.7) or India (9.4). Similar values can be observed for non-thermal services, as the current Palma
53 ratio for those services is higher than 10 in some African regions. In general, there are lower inequalities in
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the demand for heating services, which are concentrated in Southeast Asia, India, or Central Asia, where the Palma ratio accounts for 9.1, 7.5 and 7.1, respectively.

Looking forward, Figure 3 demonstrates that the differences between lower and upper deciles will decrease over time, because higher income consumers are closer to the satiation level and thus have smaller increases in consumption than lower income consumers who rapidly increase their consumption as incomes rise. Thus, inequalities in residential energy service demand will be reduced. However, the projected increase of income inequality in some regions (see Figure S6), where the demands are further from their satiation levels, entails that current inequalities in residential energy demand may persist or even worsen towards 2050. For example, in India, aggregated cooling demand is projected to rise while inequalities in cooling services are exacerbated, with the associated Palma ratio increasing from 9.4 in 2015 to 15.8 in 2050. Due to price effects, the RCP scenarios could also increase the energy inequalities in some regions and services, such as cooling in Africa Eastern or non-thermal services in India. All this information is summarized in Figure 4, which shows the region-level Palma ratios for the SSP2 narrative. The SI shows the results for additional socioeconomic narratives and RCP scenarios (Figure S14). In order to provide alternative metrics of energy inequality, we have also estimated the service-specific Gini coefficients. The evolution of the Gini coefficients of the different energy services for different scenarios, regions, and periods can be found in the SI (Figure S15 and Figure S16).

Figure 4: Palma ratio of residential modern energy service consumption per scenario, period, region, and service under the SSP2 narrative. The Palma ratio is calculated as the modern energy consumption of the top decile divided by the consumption of the bottom 40%: $Palma\ ratio = D_{10} / \sum_{i=1}^4 D_i$.

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Within-region multisector dynamics

The use of the Global Change Analysis Model (GCAM), a global integrated human-Earth system model⁴⁰ (see online documentation at <https://github.com/JGCRI/gcam-doc>), allows us to examine dynamics across a range of outcomes, such as greenhouse gas and air pollutant emissions and energy expenditures.

GHG and air pollutant emissions

In terms of emissions associated with direct residential fuel use, we find that, at an aggregate regional level, CO₂ emissions will increase over time in the Baseline scenario, while they will significantly decrease when the low-carbon transitions in the RCPs 6.0, 4.5, and 2.6 scenarios, particularly in RCP2.6. Air pollutant emissions will decrease over time in the Baseline scenario due to the assumed decrease in emission intensity. The transition to non-emitting fuels associated with the RCP scenarios causes faster and larger reductions in air pollutant emissions. The SI shows the region-level economy-wide emissions trajectories, as well as the emissions associated with the residential fuel use (Figure S17 and Figure S18).

Focusing on within-region dynamics, our results suggest that the larger reliance on traditional biomass by lower deciles results in larger emissions of harmful air pollutants such as primary particulate matter (black carbon, BC; organic carbon, OC). This implies that those lower deciles will suffer the most severe health problems associated with household air pollution. However, Figure 5 shows that the rapid substitution of traditional biomass by modern energy services directly reduces BC and OC emissions in the near-term, so the difference in exposure to indoor air pollutants between lower and upper deciles decreases over time. On the other hand, emissions for non-biomass related GHGs, such as CO₂ or hydrofluorocarbons (HFCs), are largely attributable to upper income groups, driven by their larger modern energy consumption. Considering that, in general, the differences in modern energy demand between lower and upper deciles are reduced over time (see Figure 3), differences in GHG emissions subsequently decrease for most regions and services. However, the exacerbation of inequalities in some regions and sectors, such as cooling demand in India (see Figure 4) increases the difference in HFC emissions between lower and upper deciles over time. While alternative SSP narratives and the RCPs (see Figure S19 for RCP2.6) directly affect future emission pathways, in all these scenarios lower deciles will be more impacted by household air pollution, while their contribution to direct GHG emissions (and therefore to global warming) is smaller.

Figure 5: GHG and air pollutant emissions associated with direct residential fuel use per period, region, gas, and decile for the Baseline scenario. CO₂ is reported in MTC, and other species in Gg. The line represents the SSP2 narrative, while the shaded areas represent the uncertainty ranges associated with the alternative SSP narratives. Emissions for the RCP2.6 scenario are shown in the SI (Figure S19). The figure includes a subset of the GCAM regions that covers a range of income, population, and base year fuel mixes.

Energy expenditures

We also find that there are large differences in energy expenditures as a share of income across and within regions (Figure 6). Overall, previous figures have shown that energy service demand for lower deciles is lower than for upper deciles. Nevertheless, the share of their income dedicated to energy is larger for lower deciles, with significant regional differences. In some regions (e.g., China or EU-15), the share of energy expenditures decreases from lower to upper deciles, with the highest shares observed in lower deciles (D1, D2). In other regions, such as the U.S., the highest shares are observed in low-to-mid deciles, so that the “curve” has a convex shape. This is because the differences in per capita income across deciles are larger than the differences in per capita energy service demand. The low price of traditional biomass, which composes a larger share of residential fuels in low-income groups, causes an even more pronounced convex shape in some low-income economies (e.g., Africa Eastern or India), so the highest share of income dedicated to energy is clearly observed in mid deciles, which have some access to (more expensive) modern fuels. Our results also suggest that alternative SSP-specific population, average GDP, and income distribution assumptions, and the implementation of the RCP scenarios directly affect energy expenditures (via income and price effects).

Figure 6: Share of income dedicated energy expenditures per region, narrative, and scenario in 2050 (%). The figure includes a subset of the GCAM regions that covers a range of income, population, and base year fuel mixes. An alternative representation of energy expenditures, including results for RCP4.5 and RCP6.0, can be found in the SI (Figure S20).

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Discussion

Our results show that the evolution of residential energy service demand will differ both across and within regions. While the differences in energy service demand between lower- and upper-income deciles will decrease over time as these upper-consumer groups get closer to their energy satiation levels, we find that, in some regions and services where the demands are far from being satiated, current inequalities in energy consumption can persist or even increase. This conclusion is well-aligned with recent studies that show that inequalities in residential energy access may persist if there is no specific action to reduce income inequality^{33,49-51}. The study also shows that modeling multiple dimensions of drivers of demand provides a more accurate representation of total consumption (Figure S1). The implications of considering multiple socioeconomic groups, instead of a representative consumer, is a key research topic for the modelling community and has been recently discussed by different studies^{29,52-54}.

One limitation to our methodology is that, while we include decile-specific building shell efficiency projections, potential differences in technology costs, real prices, or emission efficiencies do not vary across income deciles, while bottom-up, energy-system models may capture these more effectively. Likewise, the study does not capture the direct impacts of climate change on demand^{55,56}, which is planned to be explored in future research. While the use of income deciles to represent multiple consumers is a large improvement, the latest World Inequality Report⁵⁷, reports that around 38% of all additional wealth accumulated since the mid-1990s has gone to 1% of the people. Moreover, recent income inequality projections show that future ratios of the highest to lowest income groups will be almost three times their value using previous assumptions⁴⁵. So further disaggregation of the first and tenth deciles would provide additional insights to our results. However, doing so would require country-level projections of income distributions that break out the 1st and 99th percentiles of the income deciles used in this work, which would be a large challenge given the lack of data on current and historical income distributions at these finer resolutions. Similarly, residential end-use services have been divided into cooling, heating, and a “non-thermal” category that includes cooking, lighting, or appliances. While having a more detailed disaggregation would provide valuable information, there is no global harmonized data at energy service level (International Energy Agency balances² do not include that information). Nevertheless, additional service disaggregation could be analyzed in regions where the necessary data are available³².

Finally, this study is focused on the residential energy sector; consumer heterogeneity is not included in other end-use demand sectors, such as food, water, or transportation systems. The implementation of multiple consumers in all sectors within the GCAM modeling framework is an ongoing long-term research objective that will enable us to analyze consumer inequalities from a more holistic perspective. While future work will incorporate additional dimensions of consumer heterogeneity in all end-use systems, this study is a valuable contribution that demonstrates the importance of considering not only international but within-region inequalities in the residential sector, which is directly related to human development.

Conclusion

Recent studies show that the adoption of clean energy technologies is essential for satisfying basic human needs and improving living standards⁴⁻⁹. Given that lack of access to modern and clean energy services is heavily concentrated in lower income groups, considering consumer heterogeneity (inequality) across population groups becomes crucial for the analysis of future energy inequality. In this study we explore which is the evolution of future within-region inequalities in energy consumption, which is a major concern of decision makers and international and scientific discussions^{58,59}. This work can inform these conversations and the decision-making process.

More broadly, the study highlights the importance of considering within-region income distribution dynamics within integrated global scenario analysis, which is a major research priority for the modelling community. Considering multiple consumer groups broadens and enriches analysis^{29,60}, as it allows examination of the implications of changing economic or environmental conditions on different groups within regions, as well as the effects of different income distribution pathways on total demand, and on other associated dynamics, such as greenhouse gas and air pollutant emissions and energy expenditures.

Data and code availability

The analysis has been developed using an enhanced version of the Global Change Analysis Model (GCAM-v6.0) that has been made available in the following open-access repository: <https://github.com/jonsampedro/gcam-core>. The repository includes all the assumptions, and parameters that are read in by the model. A detailed documentation for all these input assumptions can be found in the following open-access repository: <https://github.com/JGCRI/gcam-doc>. As a relevant feature for this study, the Supplementary Information includes the data sources that the model uses for the calibration of floorspace and residential energy services (Table S1 and Table S3, respectively). The latest projections of the net income distribution used for this analysis are publicly available on Zenodo here: <https://zenodo.org/record/7474549>

The version of the model used for the analysis is accessible in the following repository: <https://github.com/jonsampedro/gcam-core>. The code for reproducing the results and generating the figures has been stored in an open-access repository (https://github.com/jonsampedro/Sampedro-et-al_ERL). As indicated in the repository, the input data for reproducing the results is available to download in Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/record/6780424#.YrznmXbMKUk>).

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Author Contribution

J.S., S.W., J.E., G.I., S.M., K.N., P.P., and M.W. contributed designed the research. J.S., developed the analysis, with contribution of all authors. J.S. wrote the first draft of the paper, and all authors contributed to writing the paper.

Declaration of interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

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